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EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY OF TRIAXIALLY BRAIDED COMPOSITE UNDER QUASI- STATIC AND HIGH SPEED IMPACT LOADINGS

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Outline

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2. Numerical Modeling Methods for Impact Simulation of Braided Composites
3. Mesomechanical Model for Triaxially Braided Composites
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5. Summary

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Part 1 Background

1. Background

➤ Applications of composite

❑ Fuselage

Boeing 787

❑ Engine fan and fan case containment

❑ Leading edge

❑ Lower wing cover

1. Background

➤ Braided composites

High damage tolerance and low manufacture cost

Woven fabrics

Triaxially braided fabrics

3D braided fabrics

➤ Mechanical response of braided composites

Architecture-dependent deformation

Axial strain of laminate composites

Axial strain of triaxially braided composite

Out-of-plane displacement of triaxially braided composite

1. Background

➤ Damage and failure in composite

Free-edge effect in textile composites

Impact failure of textile composites

Aging induced microcracking in textile composites

Fiber bridging in composite interface

1. Background

➤ Challenges

- ❑ Characterization of mechanical properties and its strain rate effect
- ❑ Impact damage and failure mechanism
- ❑ Experimental validation technology for impact response of composite structure
- ❑ Rate-dependent constitutive and damage models
- ❑ Efficient numerical simulation method for impact problem
- ❑ Virtual testing framework and structural optimization

From fundamental laboratory research to full-scale structure design

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Part 2 Numerical modeling methods for impact simulation of braided composites

2. Numerical Methods for Impact Simulation

➤ Triaxially braided composite

Carbon fiber: T700s
 24K for axial bundle
 12K for bias bundle

Epoxy resin: E862

*Experiments were conducted
 by Uakron and NASA*

➤ Properties of constituents

Property	Fiber	Matrix
Material type	Carbon T700s	Epoxy E862
Axial modulus (GPa)	230	2.7
Transverse modulus (GPa)	15	2.7
Shear modulus (GPa)	24 (Axial)/5.03 (Transverse)	1
Tensile strength (MPa)	4900	61
Density (g/cm ³)	1.8	1.2
Single fiber diameter (μm)	7.0	--

2. Numerical Methods for Impact Simulation

➤ Simulation methods of impact problem

- ❑ Meso-scale FE model (Nie and Binienda, 2014) **Low efficiency in computation**

t = 0.02 ms

t = 0.05 ms

t = 0.33 ms

t = 0.84ms

- ❑ Macro-scale subcell model (Cheng, 2006; Littell, 2008; Blinzler, 2012)

High computational efficiency

Accuracy need to improve

Failure modes cannot be distinguished

2. Numerical Methods for Impact Simulation

- Simulation methods of impact problem
 - ❑ Macro-scale homogeneous Model (ONERA, 2015 and 2016)

High Efficiency, but limited generality
Determination of parameters requires a large amount of tests

$$\underline{\underline{C}}^{eff} = \left(\underline{\underline{S}}^0 + \sum_i d_i \underline{\underline{H}}_i^m + \sum_j \left(D_j^t \underline{\underline{H}}_j^{ft} + D_j^c \underline{\underline{H}}_j^{fc} \right) + D_3 \underline{\underline{H}}_3^f \right)^{-1}$$

with $(i, j) = \{1, 2\}$

2. Numerical Methods for Impact Simulation

➤ Multi-scale modeling framework for impact simulation

Parameters of macro model determined by a **well-validated meso model**

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Part 3 Mesomechanical Model for Triaxially Braided Composites

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Geometry interpretation

➤ Identification of geometry parameters

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Finite element meshing

Top view of unit cell (matrix not shown)

Side view of unit cell

Single layer composite

Cohesive layer

Features:

1. Hexahedron elements:
Moderate stiffness, uniform size and multiple elements in the through the thickness direction.
2. Cohesive element for tow-tow and matrix-tow interface.
3. Each tow is assumed to be transversely isotropic ?

Meshing quality affects the stress distribution in the fiber tows !

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Constitutive model

- ❑ Fiber tows are considered as **transversely isotropic** material
- ❑ **Elastic and strength properties** of fiber tows can be predicted using micromechanical FE modeling or other analytical.

❑ Micromechanical RVE model for longitudinal shear

Top ($z=b$) and bottom face ($z=0$)

$$u(x, y, 0) = u(x, y, b)$$

$$v(x, y, 0) = v(x, y, b)$$

$$w(x, y, 0) = w(x, y, b)$$

Face $y=0$

$$u(x, 0, z) = 0$$

$$v(x, 0, z) = 0$$

$$w(x, 0, z) = 0$$

Front ($x=c$) and back face ($x=0$)

$$u(0, y, z) = u(c, y, z)$$

$$v(0, y, z) = v(c, y, z)$$

$$w(0, y, z) = w(c, y, z)$$

Face $y=a$

$$v(x, a, z) = 0$$

$$u(x, a, z) = u_0$$

u, v and w denote displacements in the x, y and z directions, respectively

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Damage model

□ A user-defined damage model (failure criterion and damage evolution) is developed and implemented in ABAQUS/Explicit to predict the failure of fiber bundles.

Failure Criterion

$$e_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1t}}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_{12} + \sigma_{31}}{F_{1s}}\right)^2 \geq 1$$

$$e_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1c}}\right)^2 \geq 1$$

$$e_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{2t}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{F_{1s}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_{1s}}\right)^2 \geq 1$$

$$e_{mc} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{-\sigma_{22}}{F_{1s}}\right)^2 + \frac{F_{2c}^2 \sigma_{22}}{4F_{1s}^2 F_{2c}} - \frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{2c}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{F_{1s}}\right)^2 \geq 1$$

Damage Evolution

$$G_I = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{eq}^f \varepsilon_{eq}^f l_c \quad d_I = \frac{\delta_{I,eq}^f (\delta_{I,eq} - \delta_{I,eq}^0)}{\delta_{I,eq}^f (\delta_{I,eq}^f - \delta_{I,eq}^0)}$$

Stiffness Degradation

$$S(d) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{d_f E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_{33}} & & & \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{d_m E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_{33}} & & & \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_{22}} & \frac{1}{E_{33}} & & & \\ & & & \frac{1}{d_f d_m G_{12}} & & \\ & & & & \frac{1}{d_m G_{23}} & \\ & & & & & \frac{1}{d_f G_{13}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$d_f = (1-d_{ft})(1-d_{fc}), \quad d_m = (1-d_{mt})(1-d_{mc})$$

To promote the numerical computation and smooth the stiffness degradation:

$$\dot{d}_I^v = \frac{1}{\eta_I} (d_I - d_I^v)$$

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Boundary conditions

Coupon Specimen
Justin Littell 2008

Experiment

Single Layer

6 Layers

**Axial Tension/
Compression**

**Transverse Tension/
Compression**

Periodical boundary condition is applied along the loading direction to represent the long coupon specimen.

$$\text{AT} \begin{cases} u(a, y, z) = u(-a, y, z) + \delta_1 \\ v(a, y, z) = v(-a, y, z) \\ w(a, y, z) = w(-a, y, z) \end{cases} \quad \text{TT} \begin{cases} u(x, b, z) = u(x, -b, z) \\ v(x, b, z) = v(x, -b, z) + \delta_2 \\ w(x, b, z) = w(x, -b, z) \end{cases}$$

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: axial tension (single layer)

(Zhang et al. Compos A 2014)

Fiber tension failure (fiber breakage) at global strain level 1.85%

Matrix tension failure (matrix cracking) at global strain level 0.68%

Axial fiber bundle undulation causes the discrepancy of numerical simulated and experiment curves.

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: transverse tension (single layer)

Matrix compression failure at global strain level 0.55%.

Fiber tension failure at global strain level 0.32%.

Matrix tension failure at global strain level 0.21%.

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation

Many work focus on matching the stress-strain curves, which is definitely not adequate for demonstrating the **predictive capability** of a meso-FE model, or even maybe not the correct way?

- ✓ The meso-FE should be able to capture the main failure behaviors;
- ✓ The boundary conditions of meso-FE model need to be consistent with the test condition;
- ✓ The model should be able to correlate with multiple different kinds of loading conditions.

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: surface strain

(Zhang et al. Compos A 2014)

Axial strain distribution of AT

Shear strain distribution of TT

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: free-edge effect

(Zhang et al. Mech Mater 2014)

Axial Tension

Experimental
Out-of-Plane Disp.

↑
Loading Direction
↓

Numerical
Out-of-Plane Disp.

Transverse Tension

Experiment

Numerical

← Loading Direction →

Experiment

Numerical

Out-of-plane displacement

Interlamina shear strain

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: effect of boundary condition (Zhang et al. Mech Mater 2014)

Out-of-plane deformation

The discrepancy of out-of-plane deformation originates from the different load transfer status corresponding to the boundary conditions.

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: tension (six layers)

Transverse Tension

Axial Tension

- Strain concentrated in matrix rich region between fiber tows
- The nonlinearity of stress strain curve (both AT and TT) is caused by matrix damage in fiber tows.

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: compression (six layers)

AC — Axial Strain [%]

TC — Axial Strain

3 Mesomechanical Model for Braided Composites

➤ Model validation: summary

<i>Loading Condition</i>	<i>Type of Specimen</i>	<i>Modulus (GPa)</i>		<i>Strength (MPa)</i>	
		<i>Simulation</i>	<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Simulation</i>	<i>Experiment</i>
<i>AT</i>	<i>6 layers (V_f=56%)</i>	47.6	45.7	908.6	810.0
	<i>1 layer (V_f=48%)</i>	44.9	39.0	797.2	798.1
<i>TT</i>	<i>6 layers</i>	40.7	39.0	487.3	505.0
	<i>1 layer</i>	36.8	34.1	436.6	454.1
<i>AC</i>	<i>6 layers</i>	47.7	41.4	326.5	337.4
<i>TC</i>	<i>6 layers</i>	39.6	42.7	317.9	308.7

- ❑ The predicted initial modulus in axial direction are higher than tested values due to the presence of undulation for axial fiber tows in realistic specimens.
- ❑ The overestimation of axial tensile strength for the six-layer specimen is attributed to the initial imperfection or defect in the experimental specimen, such as the squeezing of fiber tows.

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Part 4 Meso-Macro Simulation of Triaxially Braided Composites under High-Speed Impact

4 Meso-Macro Model for Impact Simulation

➤ Meso-macro homogenization

❑ Well calibrated meso-model is utilized to predict the homogenized properties of subcell components with consideration of geometry continuity.

4 Meso-Macro Model for Impact Simulation

➤ Stress-strain responses of subcell components

In-plane tensile compression and shear properties of subcell components can be predicted using the proposed meso-macro homogenization method.

4 Meso-Macro Model for Impact Simulation

➤ Model validation

(a)

(b)

(c)

4 Meso-Macro Model for Impact Simulation

➤ Model validation

❑ Failure contours layer-by-layer

- Captured not only the global crack pattern but also the intrinsic damage behavior.

5 Conclusion

1. A multi-scale modeling framework based on meso-scale FE model was established to investigate the impact failure behavior of braided composite structures.
2. The developed meso-scale FE model correlates excellently with experiments and predict well the progressive damage process of the triaxially braided composite.
3. Meso-macro homogenization method is introduced to predict the mechanical properties for each component of macro-scale subcell model.
4. The new subcell model proposed in this study shows improved accuracy in predicting the macro mechanical response of braided composite.

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Thank You!

Question?

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